

Nuclear Techniques in Agriculture Biotechnology

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Centre of Excellence in application of nuclear techniques was commissioned in this university to spearhead Nuclear Research Interdisciplinary research programs in Environmental Sciences, Industrial Biotechnology, Medical, Agriculture, Material Science, Nanotechnology. As such, this centre envisages an insight in generating professionals with specialization in Applied Nuclear techniques to achieve their prospective goals. Academic and Research activities are interdisciplinary in nature and this is to ensure that the related field would be an added advantage to those who are motivated to develop their career with specialization in Applied Nuclear Techniques in National /International arena. Joint project programs with National and International Academic, R&D Institutions and Industries are in progress.

- Nuclear techniques in Agriculture are associated with application of radiation to increase the genetic variation of cereals, oilseeds, and industrial crops as well as fruit trees
- Also, usage of radioisotopes helps to assess the mechanism of soil nutrition uptake by plants as well as fertilizer/pesticide contamination levels in Agriculture products
- Irradiation is as an effective and widely accepted method that has been endorsed by international bodies such as the World Health Organization, the Food and Agricultural Organization who judged the process to be safe without detriment to health and with minimal effect on nutritional or sensory quality.
- Evaluation of soil erosion rates by tracing cosmic Be^7 isotope

With an objective to understand the importance of nuclear techniques applications in the field of Agricultural Science, especially in the field of biotechnology, this article summarizes various aspects of agriculture biotechnology incorporating applications of nuclear techniques:

Gamma radiation induced mutation in plant breeding

In plant breeding programs, one of the oldest methods is mutation breeding. Currently, in plant biotechnology, mutation breeding has become popular among the breeders. Scientists use physical mutagens techniques (X-rays, UV light, neutrons-alpha-beta particles, fast and thermal neutrons, especially gamma rays) to artificially induce mutations (mutagenesis). However, gamma-rays are widely used. During the irradiation of the seeds with ionizing radiation to generate mutants with desirable traits, reactive oxygen species (ROS) or free radicals can be generated in cells. Usability of gamma-irradiation is to provide the permanent gene expression of antioxidant enzymes and proline through the production of ROS.

Effective method that can cause DNA changes via direct and indirect actions. Many crop varieties have been created using gamma irradiation mutagenesis technology for trait improvement that enhance the characteristic or increase the abiotic and biotic stress tolerance. Interestingly, up to 97% of the gamma irradiation mutations were concentrated in certain regions in chromosome 5H and chromosome 7H. Of the 26,745 expressed genes, 140 were affected by gamma-ray radiation; their biological functions included cellular and metabolic processes.

In recent decades, many mutation genes have been identified which are responsible for phenotype changes in mutants in various species including *Arabidopsis* and rice. Mutation feature in induced mutants and the underlying mechanisms of various types of artificial

mutagenesis remain unclear. Of the 26,745 expressed genes, 140 were affected by gamma-ray radiation; their biological functions included cellular and metabolic processes.

Due to the loss of arable lands and changing climatic patterns there is a need to develop cultivars with improved plant architecture, high yield and superior grain quality. Improved White Ponni (IWP) is one such rice variety with fine-slender grain, high yield potential, moderate resistance to tungro, rice blast, bacterial blight, mite and green leafhopper. Semi-dwarfism in rice, conferred by the *sd-1* gene, improves lodging resistance and yield. After the release of IR8 –the miracle rice by IRRI, most of the modern rice varieties were developed with the semi-dwarf gene, *sd1*.

Mechanisms of Radiation induced mutation

- ✓ Seeds of Improved White Ponni were treated with different doses of gamma irradiation (100, 200, 300, 400 and 500 Gy) in the Gamma Chamber facility (Model GC1200, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India).
- ✓ The overall agronomic performances of the IWP mutants were better than the IWP-control as studied in the M₆ generation.
- ✓ The mean performance of IWP mutants indicates a significant reduction in plant height and days to flowering.
- ✓ IWP mutants showed increased yield than IWP-control.
- ✓ A yield increase of up to 18.65 g (45.73%) in mutant WP-15-5.
- ✓ WP-15-1, WP-15-5, WP-16-1, WP-16-2, WP-16-4, WP-22-2 and WP-22-3 have recorded yield increase above 20% than IWP-control.

A1) The parent variety IWP;
A2) a semi-dwarf, early maturing and high-yielding mutant, WP-22-2 (note: the IWP is still in the flowering stage while in the WP-22-2, the panicles are already maturing); scale bar– 10 cm;
B1) Panicle of the IWP and B2) WP-22-2; scale bars– 1 cm;
C1 & C3) Rice kernels of IWP and WP-22-2; 2&C4) dehusked kernels of IWP and WP-22-2; scale bars– 2mm.